

Characterization Of Some Selected Clay Samples For Thermal Energy Storage

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ABSTRACT

This research is aimed to carry out material selection for thermal energy storage. The chemical composition was determined using X-ray Diffraction method (XRD) and the thermal behavior using Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC). The results for chemical composition showed that all samples have similarities in chemical composition but differ in their proportion. The chemical composition results are as follows Fe₂O₃, MgO, Al₂O₃, K₂O, CaO, and BaO as the major constituent with a trace of minor element. The minor element includes CuO, ZnO, Ga₂O₃, HfO₂, P₂O₅, SO₃, Cl, CaO, Cr₂O₃, and MnO. The results for thermal analysis show that; specific heat capacity of the clay samples measured at 25°C were of same value for all the clay samples which is 878 J/Kg but latent heat for clay samples from Aliero, Argungu, Birnin Kebbi and Bunza local governments were 0.219 J/Kg, 0.860 J/Kg, 0.658 J/Kg and 0.6759 J/Kg respectively. This made clay sample from Argungu a potential candidate for thermal storage because of their higher thermal properties they exhibit in comparison to another sample.

Keywords: Thermal storage, latent heat, specific heat capacity, ceramic and chemical composition.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Clay is primarily made up of the minerals silica (SiO₂), alumina (Al₂O₃), and water (H₂O), as well as significant amounts of iron oxides, alkali, alkaline earth, and a variety of crystalline substances known as

clay minerals, including quartz, feldspar, and mica (Lukman, *et al.*, 2024). The presence of these additional small oxides, or impurities, in clay in varied amounts is of significant relevance since they affect the material's technological qualities. It should be noted that the permissible amount of impurities in clay differs depending on the intended application. For instance, in the case of requiring white goods, coloring impurities such as Fe₂O₃ should not be use (Lukman *et al.*, 2024).

The utilization of clays as a primary material in prehistoric societies was widely known due to its natural occurrence and extensive distribution. Even in contemporary times, clay is still utilized in the production of a diverse range of ceramic goods such as roofing tiles, porcelain, and sanitary ware, as well as in various industrial settings. Particle size distributions, chemical and mineralogical compositions have a significant impact on the final application (Lukman, 2019).

Ceramic is widely recognized as the optimal material for employment in solar thermal storage, owing to its exceptional resistance to corrosion at elevated temperatures. Numerous endeavors have been undertaken to formulate thermal storage ceramic, as evidenced by numerous studies (Deng and Li, 2016). Recent research by Lan *et al.*, (2021) has shown that ceramic materials used in solar thermal storage mostly include alumina, silicon nitride, and silicon carbide. According to the aforementioned research, these materials are recognized for their high thermal conductivity and heat storage density. Although the oxidation and shock resistance of these materials has generated much discussion, in the research community. The attributes of materials utilized in the context of solar thermal energy storage are of paramount significance, particularly in scenarios where low temperature thermal energy storage below 50°C is required for applications such as house space heating, or in situations where high temperature thermal energy storage systems above 175°C are necessary for electrical power generation (Alva *et al.*, 2023&Kant *et al.*, 2024) .

The characteristics of the selected thermal energy storage materials are largely responsible for the efficiency of thermal energy storage systems. Based on the particular needs of the application field, the thermo-physical properties of the materials must be described. Melting point, density, latent heat of fusion, specific heat, thermal conductivity, super cooling, cost and availability, thermal stability, chemical stability, volume change, non-toxicity, non-corrosiveness, flammability, congruent melting, and vapor pressure are some of the factors that need to be taken into account (Alva *et al.*, 2023).

Clay exhibit distinctive physicochemical properties that have gathered significant attention in the field of solar thermal storage system and conversion. Furthermore, their abundance in nature, affordability, consistent thermal properties, mechanical, and fire-resistant characteristics render them viable options for large-scale systems. Despite the tendency of clay structures to assemble during charge and discharge processes, raw clay minerals are brittle. Given the aforementioned shortcomings of clays, suitable decorations and modification methods should be used to increase their effectiveness in the energy domain. Although clays are developing quickly, they have reached their full potential as useful materials for solar thermal storage system and conversion (Alva *et al.*, 2023).

Clay-based materials have a tremendous amount of potential to develop into a class of rapidly expanding solar thermal storage and conversion materials once the electrochemical properties are adjust (Voronin *et al.*, 2020)

The melting point of phase change materials should match the Thermal Energy Storage (TES) system's operating temperature range. This will enable easier charging and discharging processes. High-density materials are used, which increases the energy storage density and decreases the volume of the TES system. Additionally, a high latent heat of fusion contributes to the system's improved energy storage density. On the other hand, sensible heat storage materials require a high specific heat, which helps to increase the system's energy storage density. A high thermal conductivity is also recommended since it allows for a rise in thermal charging and discharging (Alva *et al.*, 2023).

This study may help to boost the economic growth of Kebbi state and Nigeria in general, as it has helped in discovering some of the better clay deposits among the various deposit we have in the area that can be used for thermal storage applications. The aim of this research is to among other things study the thermo-physical properties of selected samples of clay and the Objectives of the study are to; determine the chemical composition of the selected, determine the thermal properties of the selected clay samples for thermal storage application.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 The Method of Sampling and Preparation of Samples.

The clay samples were collected from a hand dug shallow holes at the selected locations. The entire areas were composed of relatively abundant deposits of clay. The clay sample was collected at random from the dugout soil at the site between depths of about 2 meters to 5 meters. The samples were crushed and thoroughly mixed by quartering and coning method in order to achieve representative homogeneous samples.

The clay samples were collected from five different locations on a particular area in order to have a good representation of the site. Four local government areas of Kebbi State were used in order to further give a wider sample spread for the state. The samples from the five locations on an area were mixed properly and a representative sample from that area was produced using the cone and quartering system as recommended by the American Society of Testing Materials (ASTM 2487) (Abubakar *et al.*, 2024). The process involves mixing the samples and spreading them uniformly and equally into a rectangle. The rectangle is divided into four equal parts and two alternate portions were taken, then mixed properly and form into a cone. The cone was also divided into four equal parts while the alternate portion was further being taken. This process of mixing properly, spreading into rectangular shapes and cones and taking the alternate portions continued until a sizable quantity sufficient for the tests to be carried out is produced (Abubakar *et al.*, 2024).

The clay samples from distinct locations within Aliero, Argungu, Birnin Kebbi and Bunza local government was obtained for comprehensive representation of the site.

2.2 Chemical Composition of Clay Samples.

The X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) technique, which is commonly employed for identifying various elements in a wide range of minerals, was carried out at the central research laboratories, Umar Musa Yar Adua University, Kastina State, Nigeria.

2.3 Thermo-Physical Properties Clay Samples

The assessment of the physical attributes of the clay samples entails an examination of multiple traits, including but not limited to, latent heat, specific heat capacity, volumetric expansion/ thermal diffusivity, mass loss, thermal conductivity and thermal shock resistance. The American Society for Testing Material (ASTM) methodology was employed to execute this endeavor.

3.0 RESULT ANALYSIS

3.1 The Chemical Composition of the Samples

The ED-XRF was carried out at Umaru Musa Yar Adua University Kastina. The results are presented in graphical form for Aliero, Argungu, Birnin Kebbi, and Bunza clay samples. Shown in figures 1 to 4 are the chemical composition of the samples for the location.

Figure 1&2 Showing Chemical composition for Aliero and Argungu Clay samples

Figure 3&4: Showing Chemical Composition for Birnin Kebbi and Bunza Clay samples

Observation on figure 1 showed that the sample contains major and minor compound as summary in table 1

Table 1 Summary of Chemical Composition for Aliero Clay Sample

Major Compound	Concentration %	Peak (cps/ mA)
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.70	6272
MgO	2.91	4
Al ₂ O ₃	8.98	140
SiO ₂	50.21	37576
BaO	1.00	0
Si ₂ O ₃	1.00	0
Traces of Minor Compounds		
Bi ₂ O	0.0450	0
Ag ₂ O	0.0008	1
MnO	0.1468	444
SO ₃	0.1383	76
Cl	0.0005	8
K ₂ O	0.3748	395
CaO	0.1267	188
Sb ₂ O ₃	1.00	0

Observation on figure 2 shows that the sample contains major and minor compound as summary in Table 2

Table 4.2 Summary of Compound Composition for Argungu Clay Sample

Major Compound	Concentration %	Peak (cps/mA)
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.91	14554
Al ₂ O ₃	15.63	244
SiO ₂	43.26	3236
MgO	2.86	4
K ₂ O	1.09	1159
Traces of minor compound		
Sb ₂ O ₃	0.5460	1
Bi ₂ O ₃	0.0439	0
Nb ₂ O ₃	0.1277	7
ZrO ₂	0.1715	274
CaO	0.3507	521
TiO ₂	0.7451	2688
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.0069	103
SO ₃	0.1633	89
Cl	0.0055	8

Observation on figure 3 shows that the sample contains major and minor compound as summary in Table 3

Table 3 Summary of Chemical Composition for Birnin Kebbi Clay Sample

Major Compound	Concentration%	Peak (cps/mA)
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.23	12022
MgO	2.85	4
Al ₂ O ₃	12.77	199
SiO ₂	46.19	3455
BaO	1.00	0
Sb ₂ O ₃	1.00	0
Trace compound		
Bi ₂ O ₃	0.0447	0
Ag ₂ O	0.0007	1
MnO	0.1589	481
SO ₃	0.1847	101
K ₂ O	0.7141	753
CaO	0.4057	603
Cl	0.0085	12
Ga ₂ O ₃	0.0019	27

Observation on figure 4 shows that the sample contains major and minor compound as summary in Table 4

Table 4 Summary of Compound Composition for Bunza Clay sample

Major Compound	Concentration%	Peak (cps/mA)
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.39	12635
Al ₂ O ₃	12.95	202
SiO ₂	44.02	3293
MgO	3.14	4
BaO	1.00	0
Traces of Minor Compound		
ZnO	0.0268	147
Ga ₂ O ₃	0.0025	35
HfO ₂	0.0010	8
Ta ₂ O ₅	0.7382	2663
SO ₃	0.1191	65
Cl	0.0093	14
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.0092	74
CaO	0.3085	458

3.2 Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Figure 5&6: DSC for Aliero and Argungu Clay Samples

The mass of the samples used for this analysis is 5.3000mg, at the heating rate of 10°C/min. the minimum point heat flow was observed at -2.22 wM with corresponding temperature of 2375 °C and maximum at 14.37 wM with temperature of 1250 °C, the onset temperature is 950 °C and end set 1500 °C. The latent heat of the samples is 0.219 J/kg.

Figure 7: DSC for Birnin Kebbi Clay Sample

The mass of the sample used for this analysis is 5.3000mg. At the heating rate of 10°C/min. the minimum point heat flows was observed at -1.90 wM with the corresponding temperature of 68.77 °C and maximum at 15.06 wM with temperature of 1263.67 °C, the onset temperature is 800 °C and end set 1550 °C. The latent heat of the sample is 0.6580 J/kg.

Figure 8: DSC for Bunza Clay Sample

The mass of the sample used for this analysis is 5.3000mg. At the heating rate of 10°C/min. the minimum point heat flows was observed at -2.90 wM with the corresponding temperature of 68.77 °C and maximum at 11.56 wM, with temperature of 1750.67 °C, the onset temperature is 800 °C and end set 1570 °C. The latent heat of the sample is 0.6759 J/kg.

Table 5 Summary of DSC for Clay Samples

Name of the Sample	Mass of sample (mg)	Thermal Conductivity(w/mk)	Heat capacity At 25°C (J/kg)	Latent heat of Sample (J/kg)
Aliero	5.3000	0.02	878	0.219
Argungu	5.3000	0.12	878	0.860
Birnin Kebbi	5.3000	0.16	878	0.658
Bunza	5.3000	0.04	878	0.676

4.0 DISCUSSION

4.1 Energy Dispersion X-Ray

From the ED-XRF all samples contain t Fe₂O₃, MgO, Al₂O₃, K₂O, CaO and BaO as the major constituent with traces of minor element in negligible amount, the minor element include CuO, ZnO, Ga₂O₃, HfO₂, P₂O₅, SO₃, Cl, K₂O, Cr₂O₃, MnO .

The alumina was present in all and thus agree with research finding where, the major refractory clay deposits containing Alumina – silicate are kaolinite and fire clay in nature with alumina content of less than 45% (Aliyu *et al.*, 2024). Observation on Table 1, 2, 3 and 4 shows that elemental composition of Aliero, Argungu, Birnin Kebbi and Bunza Clay Samples with their percentage by weight, for Fe₂O₃ 1.70%, 3.91%, 3.23% and 3.39% respectively. For Al₂O₃ they are 8.99%, 15.64%, 12.77% and 12.95%. For SiO₂ they are 50.21%, 43.26%, 46.19 and 44.02% respectively, are the major constituent of all clays samples. These compound composition are responsible for the behaviors of the clay both thermally, chemically, mechanically and sometime physically. The other minor oxide (impurities) that occur in variable quantity are important as their presence impact some properties of the clay which are of technical value, it is since, and the amount of impurity depend on the intended application. As a basic tradition in thermal storage system, raw material selection plays a vital role in the final design and the storage is strongly influenced by chemical, mineralogical composition and particle size distribution. When higher thermal conductivity material are needed, the impurities such as Fe₂O₃ must be added to the required amount.

Observation on Figure 1 to 4 it display different element in different concentration and energy level. The element are Boron, Carbon, Copper, Manganese, Iron, Yttrium, Strontium, Zinc and Zirconium. It is also observed that Iron, Strontium and Zirconium are the element with higher concentration at different energy level. The higher concentration of Iron in the clay increase the buffer capacities of all clay and kaolinite – Iron oxide complexes. A considerable proportion of the surface of clay fraction is covered by iron oxides resulting in decrease negative charge on clay and this agree with findings of (Kakoko *et al.*, 2023). The strontium is second in concentration observed from figure 4.1 to 4.7 it is responsible for the monitor of geochemical process in clayed formation as reported by (Aliyu *et al.*, 2024). Zirconium is third in concentration as observed from figures 4.1 to 4.7, it is responsible for shiny silver – grey metal, it is highly ductile and extremely resistant to corrosion and heat, the result was agreed with finding of (Kant *et al.*, 2024).

4.2 Discussion on DSC Results for Clay Samples

From Table 4.8 the specific heat capacity of the clay samples measured at 25°C was found to be same value for all clay samples which is 878 J/kg but the latent heat for clay samples from Aliero, Argungu, Birnin Kebbi and Bunza respectively found to be 0.219 J/kg, 0.860 J/kg, 0.658 J/kg and 0.6759 J/kg. Material with higher latent heat is recommended for thermal storage (Bello *et al.*, 2021), (Sharma *et al.*, 2022) and (Kenisarin *et al.*, 2022). Based on the information from the Table 5, Argungu clay samples is recommended for the f storage for its higher latent heat, it will take longer before its fully discharge. From the Table 4.8 it was discovered that Argungu has the highest thermal conductivity with the value of

0.16w/mk follow by Birnin Kebbi with 0.12w/mk then Bunza with 0.04w/mk, lastly Aliero with lowest value of 0.02w/mk.

Argungu clay sample has the highest thermal conductivity which is recommended for the thermal storage ,because it will take longer time during discharging process as reported by (Kakoko *et al.*, 2023) and (Kenisarin and Kahkamov, 2020). Thermal conductivity decreases with temperature, because of the crystalline nature of clay.

5.0 CONCLUSION

ED-XRF Results for both clay and granite samples contains the following chemical composition in various proportion such as Fe₂O₃, MgO, Al₂O₃, K₂O, CaO and BaO as major constituent with traces of minor element in negligible amount, the minor element include CuO, ZnO, Ga₂O₃, HfO₂, P₂O₅, SO₃, Cl, K₂O, Cr₂O₃, MnO

The specific heat capacity of the samples measured at 25°C was found to be same value for all the samples which is 878 J/kg but latent heat for the clay samples from Aliero, Argungu, Birnin Kebbi and Bunza respectively are found as 0.219 J/kg, 0.860 J/kg, 0.658 J/kg and 0.6759 J/kg.

Based on the information from the Table 5, Argungu clay samples is recommended for the f storage for its higher latent heat, it will take longer before its fully discharge. From the Table 4.8 it was discovered that Argungu has the highest thermal conductivity with the value of 0.16w/mk follow by Birnin Kebbi with 0.12w/mk then Bunza with 0.04w/mk, lastly Aliero with lowest value of 0.02w/mk

5.1 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this research, it's therefore recommended that, Argungu clay sample is recommended for thermal storage for its higher latent heat value , it will take long time before its fully discharge when stored heat is in used.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The institution-based research grand IBR 2024/25 sponsored by **Tetfund** of the Kebbi State University of Science & Technology, Aliero. Have well recognised by the research team and highly acknowledges the intervention upgrading and Dept of Physics KSUSTA, with which this work would have not been successful. Many thanks to our vibrant Central Research Laboratories of **KSUSTA**, and **UMYU** Katsina for given us access to their research facilities.

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